

‘Learning to do’ in the Light of Swami Vivekananda

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ABSTRACT : "Learning the Treasure Within"(1996) or popularly known Delors Commission Report was submitted to UNESCO in 1996 and according to the report one of the four pillars that ought to play pivotal role in the field of education in the 21st century is 'learning to do'. This pillar focuses putting knowledge to work, acquiring technical and professional training and developing skills for a variety of situations, implying shift from skill to competence, Dematerialization of work and the rise of the 'Service Sector'. It refers to an aptitude for teamwork and initiative, and a readiness to take risks. Learning to do as per Swami Vivekananda, that our knowledge is based upon experience. So we may read books, hear lectures, and talk miles, but experience is our teacher, the one eye-opener. It is best as it is. We learn through smiles and tears. He also said that all the wealth of the world cannot help one little Indian village if the people are not taught to help themselves. The main duty is to educate the people, so that they may learn to be self-reliant, frugal, and thus save themselves from future famine. According to Swamiji, we need technical education and all else that may develop industries so that men instead of seeking for service, may earn enough to provide for themselves, and also save something against a rainy day. He also stressed the necessity of the spread of technical education. The main aim of this paper is to look at the above mentioned pillar in the light of Swami Vivekananda's ideas.

Keywords : Learning to Do

Introduction

At the beginning of 1993, The Director-General of UNESCO felt that it was apposite moment to appraise the contemporary views and thinking in education and to receive views on what sort of vision of education would be needed to help humanity move successfully into the next century. This was the task assigned to the

International Commission on Education for the 21st Century, chaired by Jacques Delors (then President of the European Commission) and composed of fifteen prominent persons from array backgrounds and regions. The Commission held eight working sessions in all the continents (it is worth mentioning that the final report i.e. 'Learning: The Treasure Within' was adopted in New Delhi) and consulted with

a wide range of government and private groups, including eminent educators and social scientists. The Commission sought to discuss education in all its diversity and though the title of the report refers to the twenty first century, the content suggests that this report is about education in the next ten to fifteen years and not the twenty first century in its entirety.

Background of the study

The report's introduction locates the work in the tradition of Combs (1968) and Faure (1972). The report (1996) also lists a series of continuing tensions, which, though, "not new, will be central to the problems of the twenty first century". Through an understanding of these tensions the Commission invites us to take the measure of the complexity of the world in which we live and it, as if, asks us to take a new look at options that we have long considered as opposed. Understanding these tensions is absolutely necessary because at the backdrop of those tensions seemingly to be central in the 21st century the emergence of the concept of four pillars of education is deemed to be a natural, spontaneous, justified and inevitable outcome of the process. Those tensions are as follows:

- i. Tensions between the global and the local, i.e. how can we become world citizens without losing our roots?
- ii. Tension between the universal and the individual, i.e. how can the globalization of relations enrich the unique character of each individual?
- iii. Tensions between tradition and modernity, i.e. how can we adapt change without turning our backs on the past?
- iv. Tensions between long-term and short-term considerations, i.e. how can we create policies that require patient strategies in a world sustained by ephemeral?
- v. Tensions between the need for competition and the concern for equality of opportunity, i.e. how can we reconcile competition, which provides incentives; co-operation, which gives strength; and solidarity, which unites?
- vi. Tensions between extra-ordinary expansion of knowledge and human beings' capacity to assimilate it, i.e. how can we add new fields of knowledge to curricula while making critical choices?
- vii. Tensions between spiritual and the material, i.e. how can we encourage each and every one, in accordance with their traditions and convictions, to fully respect pluralism, to lift their minds and spirits to the plane of universal and in some measure, to transcend themselves? (Canadian Commission for UNESCO, 1997)

According to the authors of the report, all the tensions as already been stated above have been eating up the vitality of our present age and here lies the major challenges before the education in the 21st century to show the way out for appeasing those challenges in a peaceful but revolutionary manner.

The report, then after expounding the tensions to be overcome in the 21st century, wishes to reposition our thinking on education, to base it on four pillars namely, learning to Know, learning to Do, Learning to live together and learning to be. In order to have the fullest

understanding of 'learning to do' a little elaboration is to be made as follows:

According to the Delors' Report(1996) 'learning to do' means- a) Putting knowledge to work, b)Acquiring technical and professional training and developing skills for a variety of situations, c) implying a shift from skill to competence, d)Dematerialization of work and the rise of the 'Service Sector'. Also learning to do refers to the acquisition of practical skills as well as social and psychological skills.It refers to an aptitude for teamwork and initiative, and a readiness to take risks.It is about personal initiative and the ambition to innovate.It is about the competence of putting what we have learned into practice so as to act creatively on our environment.Learning to do enables us to turn our knowledge into effective innovations.

In the language of the Report- "Learning to know and learning to do are to a great extent in dissociable, but learning to do is more closely linked to the question of vocational training; how can children be taught to put what they have learned into practice and how can education be adapted to future work when it is impossible to foresee exactly how that work will evolve?.....Technical progress is ineluctably changing the skills required by new production processes. Purely physical tasks are being replaced by more intellectual, more mental work, such as controlling, maintaining and monitoring machines, by the work of design, study and organisation, as machines themselves become more 'intelligent' and the physical labour required for work diminishes...The demand for higher skills at all levels has a number of causes.....the Commission's consultation in developing countries indicated that these countries see the acquisition of a scientific

culture which will give them access to modern technology as the way to the future, without , however, ignoring the specific capacities for innovation and creativity to be found within the local context. This brings us back to a question that faces both developed and developing countries: how can people learn to cope effectively with uncertainty and to play a part in creating the future?"

Learning to do as per Swami Vivekananda stands as follows: "All our knowledge is based upon experience.... We may read books, hear lectures, and talk miles, but experience is our teacher, the one eye-opener. It is best as it is. We learn through smiles and tears we learn.'(C.WS.V.2009.Vol.I,P-125 & 185),b)'All the wealth of the world cannot help one little Indian village if the people are not taught to help themselves.....Educate the people, so that they may learn to be self-reliant, frugal.....and thus save themselves from future famine.....We need technical education and all else that may develop industries so that men instead of seeking for service, may earn enough to provide for themselves, and save something against a rainy day.'(C.W.S.V,2009.Vol.V,P-368). Swami Vivekananda also said,- "The training by which the current and expression will be brought under and become fruitful this called education." (C.W.IV,490.2) He also stressed the necessity of the technical education and told,- "The technical education was necessary for the industrial growth which would lead to the economic prosperity of the nation."(C.W.IV,388.1)

It is really amazing that from the 50th verse of the second chapter of the Gita where Yoga has been described as efficiency in action. "YOGAH KARMASU KUASHALAM"

.Perhaps it is for the first time in the history of spirituality, that spirituality is defined as efficiency in work (*DarkshametadIdamDharmam* – Efficiency itself is Dharma – The Mahabharata). Good workers, strong efficient farmers, industrial workers administrators, professional people, everyone must be efficient to discharge one's responsibilities to the society. This one aspect of efficiency and in the report the necessity of the type of efficiency has been given enormous magnitude but the second aspect of efficiency which has been given much stresses through-out the Bhagavat Gita by Lord Sri Krishna and the purport of which has being simply and consequently neglected in any

western model of education speaks about till more higher aim and meaning of life. This second aspects as if asks as – see what has happened to you after year of productive efficiency. Have you realized something of the divine spark that is within you? Have you gone beyond the body mind complex? In the light of Swami Vivekananda's practical Vedanta, second aspect of productive efficiency contrary to spirit of efficiency as has been made clear in the report, no doubt, stands for a higher dimension of education par excellence.

A comparative study between the concept of 'Learning to do' and Vivekananda's ideas:

Learning to Do according to Delors Commission Report	Learning to Do according to Swami Vivekananda
<p>A. Putting knowledge to work.</p> <p>B. Acquiring technical and professional training and developing skills for a variety of situations.</p> <p>C. Implying a shift from skill to competence.</p>	<p>A. "All our knowledge is based upon experience....We may read books, hear lectures, and talk miles, but. Experience is our teacher, the one eye-opener. It is best as it is. We learn, through smiles and tears we learn." (CWSV,2009.Vol.I,p.125and p.185)</p> <p>B. According to Swami Vivekananda "Educate the people, so that they may learn to be self-reliant ,frugal.... and thus save themselves from future famine.....We need technical education and all else that may develop industries so that men instead of seeking for service, may earn enough to provide for themselves, and save something against a rainy day."(CWSV,2009.Vol.V,p.368)</p> <p>C. According to Bhagavat Gita the efficiency in action is described – "Yogahkarmasukausalam". Perhaps it is</p>

<p>D. Dematerialization of work and the rise of the 'Service Sector'.</p>	<p>for the first time in the history of spirituality that spirituality is defined as efficiency in work. It is a combination of productive efficiency without and spiritual efficiency within. Efficiency is a great word and it is a great characteristic of modern western civilization. In the light of Swami Vivekananda's practical Vedanta, The second aspect of productive efficiency contrary to the spirit of efficiency as has been made clear in the report, no doubt, stands for a higher dimension of education par excellence.</p> <p>D. To develop a new frame of mind embedded in the above mentioned attributes one must increase the capacity to deal with the problems of life in the following ways :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">i. Trying to understand the workings of our own mind, and discover the root-causes of our problems.ii. Learning to detach ourselves from the mental disturbances.iii. Learning to bring out our inner transformations to solve our problems. <p>Thus self-introspection, which may be another name of concentration and which by virtue of being a component of learning to know also, serves the same purpose that learning to do is supposed to full fill in one way. Thus, if we can peer through a Vivekananda perspective, any of the first two pillars has connotations of the both.</p>
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Learning to do primarily implies the ability to put the knowledge into work or practice. We may talk and reason all our lives, but we shall not understand a word of truth, until we put it

into practice and experience it ourselves. Learning to do again bears the connotation of acquiring technical and professional training and developing skills for a variety of situations and

this especially true in the developing countries like India. Here, to be self-reliant and self-dependant are the goals of learning to do and as if it echoes what Vivekananda articulated almost century back.

Learning to do according to Delors Report mentioned dematerialization of work and the rise of the “Service Sector” where “the relationship with the material and the technology is secondary to the interpersonal relationship. The development of service sector therefore makes it essential to cultivate human qualities (intuition, flair, judgement and the ability to hold a team together) that are not necessarily inculcated by traditional training and which amount to the ability to establish stable, effective relationship between individuals” (Delors Report, 1996).

Learning to do is the acquisition of the practical skills needed in the workplace along with the ability to contribute as part of a team and to demonstrate initiative.

Learning to do represent the skilful, creative and discerning application of knowledge because one must first learn how to learn effectively, how to think creatively, critically and holistically and how to deeply understand the information that is presented, and its systematic implications for individuals and for society, in both the short and longer term.

Learning to do is another pillar of education. In addition to learning to do a job or work, this second pillar should more generally entail the acquisition of a competence that enables people to deal with a variety of situations, often unforeseeable, and to work in teams, a feature to which educational methods do not at present pay enough attention.

Learning to do demonstrate that in order to learn to live and work together productively and harmoniously, we must first find peace within ourselves, expand our acceptance and understanding of others, and continually strive towards living the values which enable us to contribute more fully to the development of a peaceful and just society.

“Education must contribute to the all-round development of each individual- mind and body, intelligence, sensitivity, aesthetics sense, personal responsibility and spiritual values.” (Delors Report)

But the report could have been more exacting if it could openly accept the necessity of self-introspection which actually develops a new frame of having the certain attributes for working as a team for collective welfare.

Here in the present study an attempt has been made to critically appraise the genesis, development and significance of the second pillar as described by Delors Report (1996) through a Vivekananda perspective.

Conclusion

Thus, learning to do describes not only how to put knowledge and learning into practice innovatively through skill development and practical know-how, but also the modalities of development of competence, life skills, personal qualities, aptitudes and attitudes. It is clear that technical and vocational education and training need to encompass all four pillars of learning in order to prepare the individual with the knowledge, skills, qualities, values, attitudes, and abilities to communicate effectively and work together productively with others. Today we must remember Swami Vivekananda as an age-old

preacher of how we can really learn to do for ourselves and continue to remember for coming days. "Science and technology have increased our knowledge of our universe..... Yet new developments in science and technology have not been an unmixed blessing. The secular culture ushered in by science has broken the unity of existence. It has replaced co-operation and interdependence with competition and struggle for survival....." (CWSV, Vol. V, p-285).

According to Swami Ranganathananda, learning to do and learning to be have to become two inseparable aspects of any education designed to help the human child to achieve life fulfilment. At present the pillar "Learning to do" is renamed as "Learning to act" (Gollob, 2011). Thus 'learning to do' means, among other things, ability to communicate effectively with others; aptitude toward team work; social skills in building meaningful interpersonal relations; adaptability to change in the world of work and

in social life; competency in transforming knowledge into innovations and job-creation; and a readiness to take risks and resolve or manage conflicts. This pillar calls for new types of skills, more behavioural than intellectual.

References

- Canadian Commission for UNESCO, (1997). *Learning Together Throughout our Lives*, Ottawa, Ontario.
- Combs, Philip. (1968). *The World Educational Crisis*, Oxford University Press, New York.
- Delors et al. (1996). 'Learning the Treasure Within'; UNESCO, Paris.
- Faure, Edgar. (1972). *Learning to Be*, UNESCO, Paris
- Gollob, Rolf. (2011). *Education for the 21st Century and Recasting Four Pillars of Education*, Zurich University, School of Education, Zurich,
- Ranganathananda, Swami. (2008). *Role and Responsibility of Teachers in Building up New India*, Advaita Ashrama, Kolkata.
- The Complete works of Swami Vivekananda (CWSV), (2006). Vol. I-VIII, 11th Edition, Advaita Ashrama, Kolkata.

Received : 18th December, 2016

Accepted : 3rd July, 2017